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Responsive communication, dissemination, and engagement plan

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Deliverable Abstract

The EOSC EDEN Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan defines the engagement strategy and planned activities to increase expert involvement in the development, testing, and validation cycles of the outputs of EOSC EDEN. This plan describes engagement with a wide range of stakeholders, e.g. through synchronisation and alignment with pertinent INFRAEOSC projects and relevant bodies under the EOSC umbrella (e.g. EOSC-A, emerging national EOSC Nodes), networks of service providers, and especially repositories and archives. The communication strategy and plan have been designed to increase the awareness of digital preservation at large and support the EOSC EDEN dissemination and stakeholder engagement activities, helping the project to maximise its impact. This Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Plan is a living document that will be updated throughout the project lifecycle. Its initial version was prepared under Work Package 4 as deliverable D4.1 and will receive its final update in 36 months.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
CC-BY	Creative Commons Attribution
CERN	European Organisation for Nuclear Research
CESSDA	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives
DCN	Data Curation Network
DDI	Data Documentation Initiative
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DOA	Diamond Open Access
DPC	Digital Preservation Coalition
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A TFs	EOSC Association Task Forces
ERIC	The European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
FIDELIS	Establishing a European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GLAM	Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
IFLA	International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions
INFRAEOSC	Enabling an operational, open, and FAIR EOSC ecosystem
ISO	International Organisation for Standardization
LIBER	Association of European Research Libraries

D.4.1 Responsive communication, dissemination, and engagement plan

LTDP	Long-Term Data Preservation
nestor	network of expertise in long-term storage of digital resources in Germany
OCLC	Online Computer Library Centre
OPF	Open Preservation Foundation
OS	Open Science
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society
PAR	Preservation Action Registries
RDA	Research Data Alliance
re3data	Registry of Research Data Repositories
RPO	Research Performing Organisations
RI	Research Infrastructures
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repositories
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium

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Executive Summary

The EOSC EDEN project is funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe framework programme and aims to support and promote digital preservation practices and standards at the European and national levels. This Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Plan outlines the strategy and activities to ensure and facilitate the engagement of relevant stakeholders in the development of the framework, model, tools, and services that EOSC EDEN will deliver throughout the project's lifetime, and to support the adoption and exploitation of the project's results.

More specifically, it will outline the plan regarding increasing expert involvement in the development, testing, and validation cycles of Work Packages (WP) 1 "*Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation*", WP2 "*Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools*", and WP3 "*Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use*" of the EOSC EDEN. It will also describe the strategic pathways towards ensuring strategic alignment with relevant initiatives such as the EOSC Partnership (including the European Commission, the EOSC Steering Board, the EOSC Association, and its most relevant Task Forces), and Data Spaces to ensure common directionality with the EOSC strategy and other developments, in collaboration with WP5 "*Coordination, Sustainability and Strategic Alignment*". Furthermore, it will seek cooperation and alignment with other INFRAEOSC projects, notably FIDELIS, and relevant bodies under the EOSC umbrella (e.g. EOSC-A, emerging national EOSC Nodes) towards engaging with networks of service providers, including trustworthy repositories and archives. A coordination mechanism will be supporting strategic alignment and facilitating collaboration on shared engagement efforts between EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS.

The main objectives of these communication, dissemination and engagement activities are a) to promote and raise awareness of the results of EOSC EDEN; b) to reach out, actively engage, and involve relevant EOSC EDEN stakeholders to gather feedback for the ongoing work and promote adoption of the outputs; c) to promote synergies between EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS in terms of long-term preservation at European and national levels; and d) ensure strategic alignment with relevant initiatives such as the EOSC Partnership. This Communication, Dissemination and Engagement Plan is a living document that will be updated throughout the project lifecycle. Its initial version was prepared under Work Package 4 as deliverable D4.1 and will be updated at 18 and 36 months.

1 Introduction

EOSC EDEN aims to promote long-term preservation of digital data at both the European and national levels by developing and implementing comprehensive frameworks, models, and practices. The goal of the project is to establish a framework for determining which data should be considered for long-term preservation, considering factors such as use, benefits, and quality. In addition, it will introduce a model for defining re-appraisal points during the data life cycle and evaluate their usability. EOSC EDEN will also identify best practices to support the development of data preservation, long-term preservation, and access strategies across Europe. These efforts will be complemented by the development of user-centric tools, services, and standards designed to facilitate the creation of a distributed European infrastructure for long-term data preservation, retention, and access.

Key initiatives of EOSC EDEN include creating a registry to integrate tools and services from trustworthy archives and repositories into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC),¹ improving and developing new services to automate preservation and curation process, and identifying standards and protocols for submitting and exchanging data packages intended for long-term preservation. To ensure that the results and outcomes of the project are adopted and sustainable in the long term, EOSC EDEN will collaborate with diverse types of stakeholders, ensuring the project outputs meet their end users' needs. One of the key stakeholders and main partner for collaboration and alignment is the HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-03 funded project FIDELIS which will establish and consolidate a European network of FAIR-enabling trustworthy digital repositories that will live on after the project finishes.² Effective communication and collaboration between both projects are critical to the success and uptake of the outcomes of the EOSC EDEN project by the growing member network of FIDELIS.

The primary goal of this Communication, Dissemination, and Engagement Plan is to strategically coordinate EOSC EDEN's activities related to engagement, dissemination, and communication with stakeholders and broader audiences at all levels, utilising various channels. This will ensure that the objectives of EOSC EDEN are successfully achieved and ensure the effective dissemination of project results to relevant scientific, and policy communities, thus maximising the value of the project. This plan also guides communication and dissemination activities carried out under EOSC EDEN, in line with the Horizon Europe Guidelines, complying in all respects with the EU principles of open science and ethics, and meeting the reporting obligations on the progress of the project to the European Commission.

This plan focuses on the following areas of work and activities to support the achievement of project goals:

- **Effective engagement with relevant stakeholders.** To engage stakeholders and foster two-way interaction, EOSC EDEN will work towards broad community engagement by utilising interactive events, surveys, workshops, and co-creation sessions. Feedback will be collected and incorporated to refine strategies, ensuring diverse voices are represented across interested stakeholder groups and thus provide positive impact to the project results.
- **Effective project communication for increasing public awareness and enhancing the visibility of EOSC EDEN.** The EOSC EDEN project information, updates and results will be shared with a wider audience through various channels (e.g., newsletter, website, socials, press releases), ensuring relevant stakeholders are well-informed about progress, key decisions, and pertinent information.

¹ EOSC. <https://eosc.eu/>

² FIDELIS. <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188078>

- **Disseminate project results to targeted audiences to foster adoption and collaboration.** EOSC EDEN will raise awareness among key stakeholders and potential users to enhance the adoption of digital preservation practices and foster collaborations through its presence and active participation at relevant events related to the EOSC ecosystem (e.g. EOSC Symposium), Open Science, and more events focussed on trustworthy digital archives and repositories (e.g. IPRES). Additionally, project outcomes will be shared with a wider audience including the scientific community (e.g. science clusters), the GLAM sector (e.g. LIBER annual conference), and policymakers (e.g. policy brief).
- **Active engagement and synchronisation with relevant projects and networks.** EOSC EDEN will closely collaborate with relevant INFRAEOSC projects, including the (by-design) sister project FIDELIS, and relevant bodies under the EOSC umbrella (e.g. EOSC-A, emerging national and thematic EOSC Nodes) towards synchronisation and alignment of engagement efforts with networks of service providers, including repositories and archives. These efforts and relevant activities will support the uptake of EOSC EDEN outputs (e.g. from WP1 and WP2) by facilitating the access to, provision of feedback for and testing of these outputs by key stakeholders, such as repositories and archives. A coordination mechanism is currently being established to act as the mediator body that will facilitate effective collaboration between projects starting with EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS, and assist in the planning and implementation of relevant engagement activities, such as three Bootcamps and (virtual) workshops for engagement at national level.

The engagement and communication plan outlined by EOSC EDEN is intentionally dynamic and iterative. Rather than presenting a fixed strategy, it serves as a living framework that will be continuously refined and expanded over the course of the project. As stakeholder relationships evolve, feedback is gathered, and specific needs and priorities emerge, the plan will be adapted to reflect these developments. This ensures that engagement activities remain relevant, targeted, and impactful, and that communication efforts are aligned with both the progression of the project and the broader EOSC ecosystem. In this way, the plan will grow in detail and precision, supporting sustained and meaningful collaboration across all stakeholder groups. An official update of the plan will be published at 18 and 36 months and will include the finetuning and further concretisation of the stakeholder mapping engagement activities.

2 Stakeholder engagement

This section provides an overview of the engagement plan for stakeholders relevant to EOSC EDEN. The detailed objectives for effective engagement and communication in the EDEN project include:

- **Identify Stakeholders:** Evaluate stakeholders based on their characteristics, engagement level and needs, communication channels, and the impact on the project (see Section 2.3).
- **Strategically Engage Stakeholders:** Community building according to key stakeholder characteristics and engagement needs, with the support of a wide range of engagement activities through interactive events, surveys, workshops, and co-creation sessions.
- **Raise Awareness of Digital Preservation:** Awareness raising and promotional activities to ensure that key stakeholders are continuously up to date with EOSC EDEN progress and developments of long term preservation processes, frameworks, and tools.
- **Incorporate Feedback:** Collect and incorporate feedback to refine strategies, enhancing the relevance and impact of project results.

Stakeholders in the EOSC EDEN project encompass individuals, groups, and organisations with an interest in or influence on the project's development, implementation, and outcomes. This includes both EOSC and non-EOSC users who require services and best practices for digital preservation, curation, and access. The section

2.3 outlines the key stakeholder groups – spanning several scientific disciplines and operating at European, national, and institutional levels – who play a critical role in ensuring the project's success and long-term sustainability. Their contributions of input, expertise, and support are essential to achieving the project's objectives.

2.1 Roles and responsibilities for engagement

In EOSC EDEN, a dedicated work package (WP4: Expert & Community Engagement) focuses on expert and community engagement activities. This work package includes all partners in EOSC EDEN consortium and is structured with dedicated teams assigned to engage with specific stakeholder groups. In particular:

- **T4.1 Coordinating the engagement with communities and experts.** T4.1 will support other WPs of EOSC EDEN in effectively engaging with communities and experts. T4.1 will establish a discussion platform for consortium partners, liaise, align, follow up, and ensure streamlined communication between WPs and specialist communities.
- **T4.2 Creating an expert curation network.** T4.2 will establish an expert curation network representing organisations, repositories (both generalist and specialist), collections/catalogues, and digital object types. This will result in data steward/curator networks with specific expertise at the disciplinary and/or digital object level.
- **T4.3 Engagement and synchronisation with relevant EOSC projects and networks.** T4.3 will facilitate engagement and synchronisation with relevant EOSC projects and networks and establish a coordination mechanism with the FIDELIS project. Task 4.3 will also identify alignment opportunities between EOSC EDEN and relevant EOSC projects, as well as other existing and emerging networks.
- **T4.4 Communication, dissemination and outreach for increased awareness and knowledge sharing on practices, standards, and tools for long-term preservation.** T4.4 will raise awareness of the temporal aspects of FAIR through dedicated communication and dissemination activities. This will ensure that practices, standards, and tools for long-term preservation are mainstreamed in the EOSC ecosystem and that the project's outputs are promoted and utilised. T4.4 will also engage with the broader landscape, including cultural heritage organisations, where preservation activities are more mainstream.

2.2 Stakeholder engagement plan

Enhancing stakeholder awareness of digital preservation, cultivating collaboration with existing organizations, communities, and initiatives, soliciting feedback, and actively engaging key stakeholders (see 2.3 Stakeholder analysis) are essential for facilitating collaboration to advance FAIR principles. As factors influencing long-term digital preservation—such as community standards, technical implementations, and the development of tools and services—continue to evolve, sustained engagement will facilitate the continuous adoption of FAIR practices over time. In particular, engagement with European trustworthy digital repository and archives networks is essential for mature preservation and FAIR-enabling practices across disciplines and geographies.³ The models developed in the project also need to be tested in multi-stakeholder use cases to validate the services provided. It is the role of WP4 Expert and Community engagement to support the other WPs in effectively engaging with communities and experts for this purpose. Figure 2 shows the main interactions between WP4 and the other work packages. Important outcomes and activities are mapped and tracked via a dedicated template on the project wiki which is meant to maintain an overview of upcoming

³ EOSC Preservation: Overview Discussion Paper <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7516259>

engagement activities. Appendix Table 1 lists the main stakeholders for each task in EOSC EDEN and the planned engagement activities.

Figure 1 – An overview of different work packages of EOSC EDEN and engagement roles per task of WP4.

2.3 Stakeholder analysis

EOSC EDEN identifies 10 key stakeholder types, with some organisations and initiatives potentially fitting into multiple categories. The primary objective is to engage these groups to test, validate, and adopt long-term data preservation tools and services, to promote the uptake of long term preservation practices, and to ensure alignment with EOSC strategic goals. Notably, an organisation/institution/initiative/community may fall under multiple stakeholder types, and we refer to their primary type based on their relevance to EOSC EDEN in this section. In general, with the key stakeholders such as trustworthy digital archives and repositories, research communities, INFRAEOSC projects, etc., EOSC EDEN will:

- Ensure representation of RIs, domain-specific repositories, archives, and service personnel to test and validate the data and process framework, with attention to domain-specific extensibility.
- Participate in co-located events (e.g., RI annual meetings, bootcamps).
- Conduct online consultations and discussions (e.g., surveys, structured interviews, and requirements gathering).

Figure 2 – An overview of the stakeholders of EOSC EDEN

2.3.1 The EOSC ecosystem

EOSC is a collaborative initiative aiming to provide a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment for European researchers, innovators, businesses and citizens. The EOSC enables a significant shift towards seamless access, FAIR management, and the effective reuse of research digital objects (including data) across scientific communities and research infrastructures. EOSC EDEN aims to enrich EOSC with new tools for digital preservation and improve how data quality is approached, assessed and maintained by repositories

and archives. Key stakeholders include the representatives and members of the EOSC tripartite governance, the EOSC Federation and the INFRAEOSC projects.

EOSC tripartite governance

The EOSC tripartite governance is the instrument for the strategic coordination between

- the European Commission (EC) representing the European Union,
- the EOSC Association (EOSC-A) representing the European research community, and
- the EOSC Steering Board (EOSC-SB) representing the EU Member States and Associated Countries to Horizon Europe Framework Programme.

The EOSC-A and the EC will be consulted to ensure the strategic alignment of the EOSC EDEN project outcomes with the EOSC strategy and the future evolution. EOSC EDEN will join the yearly INFRAEOSC projects coordination days co-organised by the EOSC-A and the EC to be informed of the strategic directions and liaise with the relevant people from the Tripartite and fellow projects. EOSC EDEN will also contribute to EOSC consultation activities organised by the EOSC-A (e.g. SRIA and MAR consultations) and provide the EC with policy recommendations for EOSC implementation via the Policy Briefs in M18 (June 2026) and M36 (December 2027).

Moreover, EOSC EDEN actively collaborates with the relevant EOSC-A Task Forces, especially the Long-Term Data Retention Task Force (LTDR-TF)⁴ and gathers additional input on FAIR and quality indicators. Many EOSC EDEN colleagues actively participate and contribute to the work of the LTDR-TF, ensuring that the outputs of EOSC EDEN are shared and the EOSC community is consulted for feedback and uptake of the work and vice-versa.

EOSC Federation

The EOSC Federation will consist of multiple EOSC Nodes that are interconnected and can collaborate to share and manage scientific data, knowledge, and resources within and across thematic and geographical research communities. At the time of writing this deliverable, the EOSC EU Node has been in operation for a few months and the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation has just begun with the 13 candidate EOSC nodes that were selected for the first wave of deployment of the Federation.

EOSC EDEN will advance the establishment of the EOSC Federation by supporting the emergence of a European distributed infrastructure for long-term data preservation, curation and access. Two important extensions to the EOSC Federation infrastructure are expected from EOSC EDEN: 1) a registry of services and repositories, with attributes reflecting the criteria of trustworthiness (defined in collaboration with FIDELIS) to mainstream tools and services from trustworthy repositories and long-term archives into EOSC; 2) a support mechanism that will guide end users, especially depositors, towards the most appropriate service for their needs. Two expert curation network events and three bootcamps are being planned to demonstrate and gather feedback on these tools and services together with the envisioned end-users. The call for participation to these events will be planned and distributed through the various communication channels in the coming months. The first activity to take place in which we will actively engage with our wider stakeholder community will be the 1st Expert Curation Event to take place in Leuven on the 1st and 2nd of October.⁵

⁴ EOSC-A Long Term Data Retention Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

⁵ Announcement Expert Curation Network event: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/events/shape-future-research-data-curation-europe>

EOSC EDEN will also explore the onboarding of services into the EOSC EU Node or other Nodes being established. Not much is known yet about the process of onboarding services into existing nodes as this is one of the topics of exploration of the current EOSC Federation Build-up phase.⁶ The project consortium will actively follow up on the progress of the build-up phase and more information on the strategy for potential inclusion of the EOSC EDEN outputs will be included in the subsequent versions of this deliverable. In addition, the EOSC EDEN consortium includes one commercial provider of long-term preservation services, Arkivum. The project will specifically investigate how well the EOSC Federation holds for private sector actors and will inform the EOSC Partnership of any lessons learnt and recommendations in this regard.

Lastly, EOSC EDEN will actively participate in the collaboration framework set up and managed by the EOSC-A to coordinate the INFRAEOSC projects' and other EOSC community players' efforts towards the strategic objectives of EOSC with minimal duplication of effort and maximal synergies. This framework includes the participation in

- the EOSC-A Opportunity Area Expert Groups
- the EOSC-A Task Forces
- the EOSC Winter School
- the EOSC Symposium
- the EOSC-A Horizon Europe Working Groups

EOSC Projects

EOSC EDEN will endeavour to collaborate and harmonise with other relevant ongoing and future INFRAEOSC projects (e.g., Skills4EOSC, FIDELIS, OSTrails, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT, EVERSE) and initiatives to embed, reuse, and extend stewardship and preservation services generated by previous or ongoing work. At the time this report is published, the project has established connections with the FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT projects ending in May 2025, with regards to uptake, reuse and further development of outputs, structures and best practices where appropriate. EOSC EDEN has early on established close connections, and venues for collaboration with the FIDELIS project (e.g. through a shared Kick-off Meeting and shared Project Management Board meetings). Further collaboration, synchronisation and exploration of opportunities for joint forces in engagement will be facilitated by the EOSC EDEN coordination mechanism (cf. chapter 5).

Key activities:

- Participate in EOSC events (EOSC Symposium, EOSC Winter School ...).
- Set-up coordination mechanism with relevant INFRAEOSC projects.
- Collaborate with EOSC-A Task Forces (notably LTDR-TF) and Opportunity Areas Expert Groups.
- Align with Tripartite Governance via INFRAEOSC project coordination days.
- Contribute to EOSC consultations on the Multi Annual Roadmap and Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda.
- Provide policy briefs (M18, M36).
- Contribute services to the Federation (Registry of trustworthy repositories and services, selection tool for depositors).
- EOSC EDEN community events: 2 Expert Curation Events, 3 Bootcamps.

⁶ EOSC Federation Build-up Phase <https://eosc.eu/news/2025/04/the-eosc-federations-build-up-phase-is-underway/>

2.3.2 Trustworthy digital archives, repositories, registries and service providers

EOSC EDEN focuses on supporting organisations that implement active core preservation practices, including trustworthy repositories, archives, registries, and other service providers. As part of its mission to foster the development of curation, long-term preservation, and access strategies across Europe, EOSC EDEN also aims to ensure the adoption and long-term sustainability of its outputs. To achieve this, EOSC EDEN identifies and engages with key stakeholder groups – particularly service providers such as existing and aspiring Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDRs), Trustworthy Digital Archives (TDAs), and relevant networks. These stakeholders play a critical role in shaping and sustaining the digital preservation landscape. Engagement with networks of service providers, including repositories and archives, is essential for community building, testing, adoption, and maximizing the broader impact of EOSC EDEN.

One of the key objectives of EOSC EDEN is to develop a registry that integrates and mainstreams tools and services from and for TDRs and TDAs into EOSC. Achieving this goal requires active engagement not only with established TDRs and TDAs but also with emerging repositories and archives to encourage broader adoption. To support stakeholder mapping and engagement, Task 4.3 initiated an internal survey in March to identify existing networks and initiatives. Additionally, a public survey was launched in early May 2025 to gather insights into current practices among digital preservation professionals worldwide. The findings from both surveys will contribute to refining and expanding the list of stakeholders to be consulted and involved in the upcoming activities of various work packages. In particular:

- WP1: Data and Process Framework for Long-term Digital Preservation will benefit from stakeholder input to shape foundational strategies.
- WP2: Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools will use these insights to guide service development and integration.
- WP3: Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation, and Future Use is already engaging with domain-specific TDR and TDA experts to gather feedback and validate project outputs.

Key Activities:

- Surveys (internal and public) to map current practices, gaps, needs and networks.
- Collaborate with FIDELIS to validate results and promote uptake.
- Involve stakeholders in WP1, WP2, WP3 for co-design and validation.
- Disseminate results at specific events targeted at TDAs and TDRs for adoption of active preservation practices and tools resulting from the project (e.g. IPRES).
- Promote the uptake of project results through activities such as targeted communication and collaborative discussions, and webinars.

2.3.3 International organisations and networks related to Open Science, standardisation and preservation

Community-based initiatives that aim to promote open science practices, establish standards, and ensure the preservation of research data are important stakeholders for EOSC EDEN. These initiatives often involve active participation from community members to foster transparency, reproducibility, and the sharing of scientific knowledge. EOSC EDEN will follow up with community-based initiatives regarding Open Science, standards,

and preservation, such as the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC),⁷ the Research Data Alliance (RDA),⁸ the GO FAIR initiative,⁹ DDI Cross-Domain Integration Framework,¹⁰ Open Preservation Foundation (OPF¹¹), and CoreTrustSeal,¹² to ensure that knowledge about digital preservation outcomes is transferred, while at the same time receiving feedback from these communities. They are crucial stakeholders for engaging throughout the project, such as the identification, selection, and appraisal of data for long-term preservation and designing long-term access and preservation services and tools. Additionally, they will benefit from the EOSC EDEN project's outcomes by advocating for the models and services provided. Keeping them informed of the project outcome through newsletters, workshops, and seminars will be advantageous.

Key activities:

- Continuous engagement through newsletters, seminars, and feedback loops.
- Disseminate results to a broader audience interested in Open Science practices to create awareness on the importance of preservation, to influence standards development and to promote the adoption of standards recognised by EDEN

2.3.4 Discipline-specific communities

In the present document, discipline-specific communities refer to the groups of researchers and professionals focused on a particular field or discipline, and community members who collaborate to advance knowledge, share best practices, and address common challenges within their area of expertise. Effective engagement with discipline-specific communities is critical to EOSC EDEN. Discipline-specific communities can provide valuable feedback and domain-specific insights during the design of reappraisal models for long-term data preservation. Their expertise ensures that the models are tailored to the unique needs and practices of different fields. The various terminologies used across disciplines for appraisal processes and metrics will be collected and mapped, which will, in turn, benefit these communities. The reappraisal model will consider representative scenarios from various disciplines and data types where reappraisal is deemed appropriate.

The EOSC EDEN consortium represent 7 different discipline specific communities¹³ who will co-design a pilot methodology composed of discipline-specific user journey maps (e.g., for Climate Simulations, Earth and Environmental Science), tools, framework-testing procedures, and user acceptance criteria. The implementation will be a series of iterative workshops and consultations on awareness, understanding, and maturity of preservation activities to demonstrate and validate the utility of LTP frameworks and tools developed in the project. Active engagement will be conducted with disciplinary stakeholders such as Data Preservation in High Energy Physics¹⁴ and the International Society for Biocuration¹⁵. EOSC EDEN will also collaborate with Research Data Alliance (RDA)¹⁶ affiliated groups that focus on disciplines, interdisciplinarity, and/or specific object types (e.g., the Vocabulary Service IG) and with preservation networks and member organisations to embed project outcomes sustainably. In addition, the long-term preservation framework and

⁷ Digital Preservation Coalition. <https://www.dpconline.org/>

⁸ Research Data Alliance. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁹ GO FAIR initiative <https://www.go-fair.org/go-fair-initiative/>

¹⁰ DDI Cross-Domain Integration. <https://ddialliance.org/ddi-cdi>

¹¹ Open Preservation Foundation. <https://openpreservation.org/>

¹² CoreTrustSeal. <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

¹³ Disciplines and representative partners within EOSC EDEN: Climate Simulations (DKRZ), Earth & Environmental Sciences (UBREMEN), Food Sciences (Premotec), High-Energy Physics (CERN), Life Sciences and Bioinformatics (SIB), Linguistics (UiT) and Social Sciences (KNAW and UESSEX-UKDA)

¹⁴ Data Preservation in High Energy Physics. <https://dphep.web.cern.ch/>

¹⁵ International Society for Biocuration. <https://www.biocuration.org/>

¹⁶ Research Data Alliance. <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

tools will be validated across various disciplines through pilot testing. EOSC EDEN will offer a support kit to empower discipline-specific and data type-oriented communities to adopt these practices.

Key activities:

- Engage with scientific disciplinary repositories through embedded partners (7 disciplines directly represented in the consortium) and the science clusters.
- Co-design pilots using user journeys, iterative workshops, domain-specific feedback.
- Map and standardise discipline-specific terminologies and reappraisal metrics.

2.3.5 Research performing organisations

Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) are institutions primarily engaged in conducting research, which can be public or private, such as universities, research institutes, and specialized research centres. Under EOSC EDEN stakeholder analysis, these organizations are considered key stakeholders because they play a crucial role in generating knowledge and data, driving innovation, and designing data policy at institutional level. Engagements with RPOs involve two main aspects. The first is understanding their needs and challenges regarding data policy, particularly in open science and digital preservation. This can be achieved by involving representatives from research data support departments or data curators for institutional repositories through the planned expert curation network events. These representatives will also be approached for surveys and interviews to gather valuable insights. Second, EOSC EDEN will enhance institutional awareness by offering consultations on digital preservation activities, processes, and challenges, to ensure that RPOs are well-informed and consider these aspects when designing regulations for the preservation of research data. This will also benefit partners embedded within RPOs, such as CERN, KU Leuven, and TiB, but also external stakeholders. EOSC EDEN will leverage its engagement activities to reach a broader range of organisations and institutions facing preservation challenges.

EOSC EDEN will build a curatorial network to study roles and responsibilities, quality (technical and standards compliance vs. scientific), and value assessment criteria. In addition, through data stewards, researchers, or information managers, EOSC EDEN will raise awareness of long-term preservation actions and processes during the lifecycle management of research objects and awareness of EOSC EDEN project outputs (e.g., registries, practices, support toolkits). Particularly, EOSC EDEN will engage data stewards with strong disciplinary and/or data type-specific backgrounds to conduct requirements gathering (surveys, semi-structured interviews).

Key activities:

- Peer to peer exchange to raise awareness on digital preservation at institutional level (data stewards, institutional repository managers) through embedded RPO partners (e.g. CERN, KU Leuven, TiB).
- Engage via surveys, interviews, and curation workshops.
- Promote uptake of EDEN practices / services

2.3.6 Research infrastructures

Research infrastructures (RIs) - whether national, European, or intergovernmental - provide essential resources and services that empower research organizations and communities to conduct studies and drive innovation. These infrastructures can be single-sited or distributed, and their applications extend beyond research to include education and public services. EOSC EDEN will actively engage with RIs including:

- The European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERICs)¹⁷ such as ACTRIS ERIC, CERIC-ERIC, CESSDA ERIC, DARIAH ERIC
- The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) and its e-Infrastructures Group, ESFRI-EOSC Coordination Task Force, EIROforum
- National research infrastructure, such as the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)¹⁸

As most RIs are responsible for conducting and supporting research, as well as archiving the data generated, they are crucial stakeholders to EOSC EDEN. Understanding their awareness and potential/implemented actions towards digital preservation, along with their needs, is essential. This can be achieved through research approaches, such as surveys or interviews. EOSC EDEN can further enhance digital preservation awareness among RIs and highlight key project outcomes, such as frameworks for identifying data for digital preservation and re-appraisal models.

Key activities:

- Conduct surveys/interviews to assess digital preservation readiness.
- Involve research infrastructure data curators in EOSC EDEN curation workshops.
- Promote EOSC EDEN outcomes (frameworks, reappraisal models) through research infrastructure specific community events and meetings (e.g., NFDI webinars).
- Promote uptake of EDEN practices / services

2.3.7 GLAM sectors with well-established preservation actions

The GLAM (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, and Museums) sector has long maintained robust preservation practices. With the increasing integration of the FAIR principles and the 'Collections as Data' movement, there is significant potential for mutual benefit through collaboration on frameworks, guidelines, and best practices for the identification, selection, and appraisal of data for long-term preservation and other strategic outcomes.

Engagement with key organisations—such as the Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER), the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA), the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage (Europeana), and other trusted digital repositories (TDRs) within the GLAM sector – will be relevant to gather feedback on the current practices for the identification, selection, and appraisal of data for long-term preservation in this sector. EOSC EDEN will actively collaborate with GLAM preservation experts by conducting surveys, and will disseminate insights and project outcomes through relevant communication channels and events such as the LIBER annual conference for the promotion of practical toolkits and resources for broader application.

Key activities:

- Disseminate information through GLAM specific communication channels (e.g. LIBER newsletter).
- Promote preservation toolkits and best practices at GLAM-focused events (e.g. Europeana community events).

¹⁷ European Research Infrastructure Consortium. https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric/eric-landscape_en

¹⁸ German National Research Data Infrastructure. <https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en>

2.3.8 National networks related to Open Science and preservation

EOSC EDEN will develop the necessary expert curation and speciality networks, which will consist of various representations from national networks, which will form a key EOSC EDEN outreach strategy. Representatives of initiatives active at the national or regional level will be involved across the project phases and action lines, with a special focus on digital preservation implementation. EOSC EDEN will provide guiding information on becoming members of the European network of trustworthy repositories that is being established in the context of the FIDELIS project, consult with global or national digital archives, repositories, and registries on preservation activities, processes, and challenges through participation in Bootcamps and synchronisation to gather feedback on user requirements and facilitate application and exploitation of project results.

For national networks, such as the Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN)¹⁹ and Dataverse national networks (e.g., Dataverse Belgium, DataverseNL²⁰), peer-to-peer knowledge exchanges will be organised with national projects and networks related to input and uptake of project results to increase understanding of the temporal aspects of FAIR and the importance of LTP-related data and services.

Key activities:

- Boost participation, feedback and uptake of EOSC EDEN outcomes through embedded local contacts of the consortium partners.
- Disseminate results to national networks, where possible and relevant in local language.
- Provide a guide on joining emerging networks (e.g. expert curation network).

2.3.9 Research funding organisations and Policymakers

Research funding organisations

Research funding organisations that focus on supporting Open Science, FAIR data, standards, and digital preservation are key stakeholders for EOSC EDEN. EOSC EDEN will actively engage with relevant European or national research funding organisations, funding mechanisms, and bodies (e.g., Horizon Europe, Science Europe, E-ARK Foundation). The goal is to establish a common understanding of the temporal aspects of the FAIR principles and the importance of LTDP-related services. EOSC EDEN will raise awareness about the often-underestimated temporal side of FAIR and the criteria for data preservation within this framework. EOSC EDEN will provide a set of recommendations and guidelines regarding digital preservation, which will be valuable for future grants and funding mechanisms, ensuring that EOSC and EU funding is well distributed. This engagement also aims to advocate for digital preservation to be more explicitly integrated into the design of funding opportunities.

Policymakers

Policymakers encompass national and EU-level actors who shape policies related to research infrastructures, open science, and data governance. This group includes national parliaments and ministries, research councils, and the European Commission and Parliament. They also allocate funds to topics relevant to the broader European landscape. Policymakers play a crucial role in ensuring that open science and long-term data preservation strategies align with broader policy agendas, such as the European Research Area Policy

¹⁹ Flemish Research Data Network. <https://www.frdn.be/nl/#>

²⁰ Dataverse Belgium; <https://github.com/libis/rdm-dataverse-belgium/wiki> DataverseNL. <https://dataverse.nl/>

Agenda²¹, and funding priorities. Their involvement is crucial for the successful integration of the strategies and recommendations generated by EOSC EDEN regarding digital preservation into the broader research and innovation framework. EOSC EDEN will support the EU' strategic goals related to Open Science and FAIR data.

EOSC EDEN will advocate the importance of LTDP-related practice and services to funders and aim for the future integration of preservation concepts into policy frameworks. To facilitate broad uptake and increase the impact of EOSC related project outcomes, EOSC-A has established a Horizon Europe Impact group which provides different mechanisms for the demonstration of project results to stakeholders such as funders and policymakers. This happens through the formulation and publication of Key Exploitable Results (KER) and the support towards adoption of the Sustainable Exploitation Planning (SEP) methodology. In addition, policymakers will be invited to participate in seminars/meetings later in the project to gain insights into the outcomes of EOSC EDEN and importance of preservation to ensure digital objects and other research outputs remain FAIR over time. These sessions will help them understand challenges such as limited availability of resources (e.g., energy and capacity) and high maintenance requirements (e.g., diversity of formats and community needs), as well as recommendations for long-term data preservation. This provides an excellent opportunity to showcase the project's value and how its results can inform and support more effective policies regarding research data, the temporal aspects of the FAIR principles, and long-term preservation. Additionally, a final policy briefing will be published in month 36, offering insights and recommendations from EOSC EDEN to guide policy developments.

Key activities:

- Advocate with funders for integrating preservation criteria and costs into funding criteria, i.e. via Horizon Europe Impact group.
- Host seminars/briefings to inform policy on digital preservation needs.
- Provide policy briefs (M18 and M36).

2.3.10 Data Spaces

Together with stakeholders under the Digital European Program,²² such as the Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC),²³ Common European Data Spaces,²⁴ EOSC EDEN's actions include consulting on the preservation awareness and activities of the European Common Data Spaces consortia and establishing a dialogue with the most relevant data spaces, such as the European Data Space for Cultural Heritage²⁵ which serves the GLAM sector, one of our main stakeholder groups, to explore information exchange on preservation practices and requirements and thus promoting the adoption of project results.

Key activities:

- Consult on preservation awareness and strategies.
- Promote cross-sector adoption (e.g. via DSSC).

²¹ European Research Area Policy Agenda. https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2021-11/ec_rtd_era-policy-agenda-2021.pdf

²² Digital European Program. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme>

²³ Data Spaces Support Centre. <https://european-digital-innovation-hubs.ec.europa.eu/knowledge-hub/digitisation-projects-and-initiatives/data-spaces-support-centre>

²⁴ Common European Data Spaces. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

²⁵ Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage <https://www.dataspace-culturalheritage.eu/en>

2.4 Engagement channels and mechanisms

Various channels will be utilised to conduct the engagement activities, ensuring that the project's key outcome and feedback effectively reach each stakeholder group. These channels include:

- Online surveys and semi-structured interviews
- Organising interactive (face-to-face and virtual) engagement and knowledge exchange events, including bootcamps, webinars & meetings
- Participating in third-party events (see Table 1)
- Activities with community-specific and/or geographical character

2.4.1 Online surveys and semi-structured interviews

Online surveys will be used to gather information and feedback from various communities. To achieve an overview and evaluation of existing frameworks, guidelines, and practices that guide the identification, appraisal, and selection processes of data for long-term digital preservation, desk research and surveys will be conducted. The timing and topics of the surveys will be determined based on the EOSC EDEN timeline of activities and ongoing events and webinars. EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS aim to leverage synergies in surveying shared target stakeholder groups. To avoid survey fatigue, the two projects will aim to collaborate where appropriate, but also share questions and results (after anonymisation of sensitive information) between the two projects. Standardised informed consent information will be required to be included for each survey, and detailed data management regarding privacy and storage can be found in D5.2 EOSC EDEN Data Management Plan²⁶.

Semi-structured interviews will be conducted as a stand-alone tool and to follow up survey responses, as needed, to collect user stories and community norms and expectations, focusing on disciplinary, cross-disciplinary, and data type-related requirements and needs. Interviews with discipline-specific researchers and repository managers are ongoing (T3.1) and will be elaborated on later in this document.

2.4.2 Engagement and knowledge exchange events

In the course of EOSC EDEN, a number of engagement and knowledge exchange events will be organised. These events will target the whole spectrum of stakeholder groups identified in section 2.3, but diversification is expected according to the project's activities and stakeholder special characteristics and needs. Wherever possible, events and meetings will be made available for virtual audiences, and webinars will be organised to ensure maximum outreach to stakeholders and the wider community. Community-specific characteristics (e.g. under-represented countries), disciplinary and geographical aspects, as well as diversity and inclusion criteria will be considered while planning. Collaboration with other entities and initiatives, where appropriate (e.g. INFRAEOSC projects like FIDELIS, OSCARS, Skills4EOSC, EVERSE, EOSC mandated organisations and Nodes, EOSC Task Forces, etc), will be sought. Examples of such events are described below:

Two curation workshops will be organised in years 1 and 2 (T4.2). These events will be 2-day physical gatherings focused on intensive learning and discussions with curation specialists. The participants at these two events will provide valuable input for the collection and evaluation of good practices in the project's outcome. The events will also provide input and feedback on the Curation network handbook (D4.2).

Three Bootcamps for repositories, archives, and registries will be organised (T4.3) to ensure the co-creation and the adoption of the project's results. These Bootcamps will align with the support and training

²⁶ Wyns, R., Zhang, F., Märkälä, A., Conzett, P., & Lindlar, M. (2025). D5.2 EOSC EDEN Data Management Plan (Version v1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15119951>

mechanisms of the FIDELIS project to ensure the participation of existing and aspiring trustworthy repositories. At the moment this report is published, a coordination mechanism between the two projects is deployed to identify a common approach for these Bootcamps, as well as begin the planning for the first Bootcamp to be held in Q4 2025. Topics identified for the first bootcamp include knowledge exchange activities and feedback on relevant EOSC EDEN outputs (e.g. D2.1 EOSC EDEN specifications and architecture (first iteration)), as well as relevant activities, services, practices and tools that are already available and appropriate for long-term preservation. Alignment with FIDELIS will allow more targeted engagement with the community, as well as the application of training approaches made available under the FIDELIS support programme.

A series of (virtual) engagement activities will be deployed for engagement of relevant national initiatives (T4.3) starting with the involvement of project partners and the countries with emerging EOSC Nodes. Collaboration with FIDELIS will be sought as appropriate, while also building upon best practices for such engagement (e.g. FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshows).

To ensure that solutions are widely promoted and transferable to relevant actors in the EOSC ecosystem, including (existing and future) EOSC stakeholders, EOSC EDEN will coordinate meetings with EOSC-A activities and with the INFRAEOSC projects as necessary, and/or will invite their representatives in relevant activities.

2.4.3 Participating in third-party events

In addition to surveys, interviews, workshops, and bootcamps, EOSC EDEN representatives will actively participate in third-party events relevant to digital preservation, conferences or workshops organised by EOSC-A, the sister project FIDELIS, or network organisations like RDA or other INFRAEOSC projects. This will ensure the sustainable embedding of project outcomes. Furthermore, EOSC EDEN will actively contribute to the EOSC Partnership event and activities to increase alignment with and adoption of its results in the ecosystem. EOSC EDEN will work closely with the EOSC Task Forces, especially the Long-Term Data Retention Task Force.

Table 1 – Past and upcoming third-party events relevant to EOSC EDEN in 2025, to be updated

No.	Key Facts	Location	Date	Audience
1	EOSC Winter School	Sevilla, Spain	January 2025	Representatives from the EOSC-A Board, EOSC-A Secretariat, European Commission, HE EOSC-related projects, Opportunity Area Expert Groups, and the EOSC-A Task Forces.
2	FAIRfest	The Hague, NL	February 2025	Researchers and data practitioners, data stewards, data service providers and repository managers, research performing organisation staff, open science national level initiatives, and representatives of projects, initiatives, and actors in both EOSC and FAIR ecosystems.
3	Dataverse Community Meeting	Chapel Hill, USA	June 2025	Researchers, librarians, developers, data professionals, and anyone interested in data sharing, repositories, and research data management
4	EOSC Project coordination meeting 2025	Brussels, Belgium	June 2025	EOSC-related projects funded under Horizon Europe,
5	Open Science FAIR	Geneva, Switzerland	September 2025	Research communities and infrastructures, libraries, repository managers, content providers, service providers research administrators and facilitators of research,

				learned societies, publishers, policymakers and funders, citizen science groups and initiatives, innovators in scholarly communication.
6	The 7th International Open Search Symposium	Helsinki, Finland	October 2025	Researchers, data centres, libraries, policymakers, legal and ethical experts, and society
7	Open Science Conference	Hamburg, Germany	October 2025	Researchers, data stewards, librarians, practitioners, infrastructure providers, policymakers
8	International Data Week 2025	Brisbane, Australia	October 2025	Data scientists, researchers from various fields, data stewards, interoperability and informatics experts, industry leaders, entrepreneurs, and policymakers.
9	EOSC Symposium 2025	Brussels, Belgium	November 2025	Diverse group of stakeholders involved in Open Science, including researchers, data stewards, librarians, practitioners, infrastructure providers, policymakers, and other relevant groups.
10	iPRES 2025	Wellington, New Zealand	November 2025	Archivists, librarians, researchers, policymakers, and professionals from various cultural, media, and government sectors

2.4.4 Community-specific outreach approach

To ensure that digital objects remain understandable and usable to their community of users over time, EOSC EDEN representatives will actively engage with various disciplines and cross-disciplinary communities. EOSC EDEN will pursue a structured and informed approach to establish the necessary skills and resources to support both intra- and cross-disciplinary, as well as data type-based, communities in establishing and enforcing suitable LTDP and access strategies and processes.

Seven scientific disciplines represented in EOSC EDEN consortium (DKRZ: Climate Simulations, UBREMEN: Earth & Environmental Sciences, PMT: Food Sciences, CERN: High-Energy Physics, SIB: Life Sciences and Bioinformatics, UiT: Linguistics and KNAW & UESSEX-UKDA: Social Sciences) are key to ensure successful uptake of the project outputs delivered by WP1 and WP2 and enhance the sustainability of long-term preservation among the scientific community in Europe. These representatives of the scientific disciplines act as early adopters, and they develop discipline-oriented pilots to test the EOSC EDEN outputs from a discipline-perspective. They will identify and analyse diverse needs and challenges that each discipline has and transform them into requirements and feedback for the partners in charge of developing the framework, tools and services in WP1 and WP2. They will also contribute to the creation of a support-kit to guide and support new users in adopting the results of EOSC EDEN. The support-kit will contain different materials e.g. a how-to-get-started guide, discipline-specific as well as cross-disciplinary and data type-oriented guidelines and checklists, training materials, a concept to provide feedback and communicate across interested communities after the project has ended.

Another important mechanism to support uptake is the Curation Network that EOSC EDEN will establish during the first project year. The Curation Network will help communities adopt, adapt, promote and expand the developed data quality function and tools among the European research ecosystem. It will provide stakeholders with a platform for knowledge exchange and collaboration and will support national, institutional, discipline-oriented and other specialised repositories and archives in harmonising their curation practices.

In addition, EOSC EDEN will organise three bootcamps for repositories, archives and registries to ensure the co-creation and the adoption of the project’s results. EOSC EDEN will collaborate with FIDELIS training programme on the bootcamps to ensure participation of existing and aspiring trustworthy repositories.

To secure the representation of less visible disciplines in the EOSC ecosystem, EOSC EDEN will interact with data stewards, particularly those providing domain-specific support, through national Open Science (OS) networks.

Dissemination of outcomes from different work packages to relevant communities will be supported by additional webinars where needed and other communication efforts.

Table 2 presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) used to monitor and assess the effectiveness, reach, and impact of engagement activities carried out within EOSC EDEN.

Table 2 – KPIs for engagement activities in EOSC EDEN

Action	Channels/Tools	Indicator	KPI
Curation workshops	In-person meetings	# of events	S: 2
		# of experts in the network	S: 50
Bootcamps	In-person or online meetings	# of bootcamps	S: 3
		# of participants in total	S: 200
Workshops, webinars & trainings	In-person or online meetings	# of bootcamps	S: 5
3rd party events	In-person or online meetings	# of participated events	S: 30

Note: B, beginning of the project; S, summary or the end of the project.

3 Communication plan

To effectively implement the activities outlined, the project will maximise its visibility and impact using a set of channels and tools specifically tailored to different target audiences. We aim to (1) raise stakeholders' awareness of long-term preservation and foster collaboration to promote digital preservation and (2) share project results and outcomes with a wide audience through various channels. Key actions and KIPs are listed below.

3.1 Project key facts

To allow for transparent, clear and effective communication about EOSC EDEN, partners are provided with a list of key facts (cf. appendix 2). This will ensure alignment across the consortium and a good base for translating purposes when partners wish to communicate about the project in their local languages.

3.2 Branding

EOSC EDEN has dedicated branding in line with the co-branding guidelines for Horizon Europe INFRAEOSC Projects²⁷. The guidelines were developed by the EOSC Association to ensure a unified branding approach

²⁷ <https://zenodo.org/records/11049140>

across the EOSC ecosystem, with an identifiable visual linkage to the branding of the EOSC Association itself. 'Branding' refers to all activities, materials and actions that influence the project's visual appearance.

3.2.1 Visual Identity

Figure 3 – Co-branded EOSC EDEN logo by the EOSC Association

In line with the co-branding logo and brand guidelines, the logo of EOSC EDEN is designed and will be applied to the website, social media, printed materials and all presentation and communication channels. The EOSC EDEN logo contains an icon as well as the name of the project. It is provided in three different colours to allow for multiple use and accessibility.

The favicon and profile picture are made of the icon from the logo and project name. An example can be seen in figure 4 below.

Figure 4 – Co-branded EOSC EDEN icon by the EOSC Association

3.2.2 Colours

The three official brand colours present in the EOSC EDEN logo are designed as lively green combined with mild pink and warm black. The project also develops a range of templates for PowerPoint presentations, deliverables, reports, and virtual backgrounds to enhance the visibility and promotion of EOSC EDEN's activities and results. A project banner was developed to be displayed at project meetings or workshops. These marketing materials will raise awareness of the brand and also serve as a tool to effectively engage stakeholders and the wider community, strengthening the impact and significance of EOSC EDEN's contribution to the EOSC ecosystem.

D.4.1 Responsive communication, dissemination, and engagement plan

Figure 5 – Colours of EOSC EDEN branding by the EOSC Association

3.2.3 Communication materials

Different communication materials have been prepared in the EOSC EDEN branding for usage by the partners in their outreach activities. These currently include a deliverable reporting template, a PowerPoint presentation template, a virtual background for online events and a roll-up banner with all the partner logos.

The EOSC EDEN project PowerPoint template has been developed for all partners to utilise in both public and internal presentations. Various slide layouts allow for the presentation of graphs, pictures, tables etc., while keeping the brand visual identity intact.

Here is your title

Here goes the subtitle - remember to use British English

01/01/2025 by Name Surname

Figure 6 –EOSC EDEN PowerPoint template

A poster template is under preparation, and more materials will be designed in the coming months when required. EOSC EDEN aims to keep its ecological footprint low and will thus carefully consider any print materials. As an alternative, ideas such as printing simple business cards directing to our online presence and latest news are considered. The communication kit comprising EOSC EDEN communication materials is available in the project's shared document space and will be made available on the project website²⁸.

3.3 Communication channels

3.3.1 Website

A joint website for EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS was launched on 31st March 2025 (<https://eden-fidelis.eu/>) to provide a unified platform where stakeholders can track the progress and achievements of both projects, contribute to ongoing activities, and collaborate effectively.

The rationale for creating a combined website stems from the significant overlap in stakeholders and the strong linkages between the workplans of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS. Both projects operate within the same ecosystem of digital preservation and research infrastructure, and they share common goals and complementary activities. Maintaining separate websites could lead to confusion among stakeholders, who

²⁸ <https://eden-fidelis.eu/communication-kit-eden-fidelis-project>

might struggle to find consistent and up-to-date information across two platforms. By integrating the two projects into a single online presence, we aim to streamline communication, reduce duplication of effort, and provide a clear, centralized location for accessing information about advancements in digital preservation. This approach enhances visibility and coherence, making it easier for stakeholders to engage with the projects. To ensure transparency and clarity—especially for the European Commission and other key audiences—individual project activities such as webinars, news updates, and stakeholder engagement opportunities are clearly labelled as being organized by EOSC EDEN, FIDELIS, or jointly. This labelling helps maintain project identity while reinforcing the collaborative nature of their efforts.

The website displays project information and expected outcomes, events, and media. The partner logos are included in a carousel on the homepage. Key implementation outcomes such as the framework, re-appraisal model, and support toolkit will also be available on the website. During the project, the website will undergo different iterations, aligning with the development of major activities, milestones, and deliverables of the project.

3.3.2 Newsletter

On the homepage of the joint EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS website, users are invited to subscribe to a shared newsletter—an essential communication channel designed to connect the projects with the broader EOSC ecosystem and beyond. The joint newsletter serves as a streamlined and efficient way to keep stakeholders informed about the latest developments, upcoming events, funding and collaboration opportunities, and other relevant updates from both projects. By combining content from EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS into a single publication, the newsletter avoids duplication, reduces information overload, and ensures that readers receive a coherent and comprehensive overview of activities in the digital preservation landscape. This integrated approach not only strengthens outreach and visibility but also reinforces the synergies between the two projects. It helps build a more connected and informed community, encouraging engagement and uptake of project outcomes. As of the end of June 2025, the newsletter has 235 subscribers, and the second edition is scheduled for release on 1st July.

All newsletter subscriptions are managed in full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), ensuring that personal data is handled responsibly and transparently. Additionally, where appropriate, the newsletter content will be shared via other relevant mailing lists – such as those of project partners, research institutes, and open science communities – to further amplify its reach.

As with the website, the joint newsletter reflects the collaborative spirit of EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS, offering stakeholders a single, trusted source of information that supports clarity, coordination, and community building.

Figure 7 – Homepage of the joint EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS website, featuring newsletter subscription

3.3.3 Social media

The social media presence will communicate project progress, findings, news and events and is expected to impact the audience in an accessible and engaging way. Social media accounts are established on relevant platforms such as [LinkedIn](#), [Bluesky](#), and [YouTube](#) to promote participation in project activities and extend the impact of the results to a wider community. During the life of the project, other social media platforms may be identified and utilised to further expand our reach.

- LinkedIn: There are two aspects to this platform; an EOSC EDEN page and a group. The page is like a virtual company business card and should have more static content, event postings etc., while the group is designed to attract stakeholders (followers) who will interact with the project partners and each other. Posts should be tailored for professional and academic audiences, leveraging long-form articles, persistent media (such as videos and podcasts), and discussions. Engagement with project and policy stakeholders should be a priority.
- Bluesky: Posts should maintain a more conversational tone while still aligning with project objectives. Content can be more experimental and interactive but should maintain professional integrity.
- YouTube: This channel will be used for the dissemination of videos from webinars, events and other resources. Each uploaded video should contain a title and short description with links to the website. The videos should also be embedded on the project website.

The EOSC EDEN social media posts will disseminate important milestones, project progress and outcomes, opportunities to give input, highlight news and events, and (in the case of the LinkedIn group) encourage knowledge sharing, interactive dialogue and collaboration. Social media posts' content will avoid excessive technical jargon while maintaining accuracy, especially when explaining complex aspects to non-specialist audiences. The project uses British spelling when writing in English (for example using -ise rather than -ize, Centre rather than Center, Colour rather than Color, etc.). When publishing social media posts, project partners should focus on:

- Project updates, including milestones, publications, and outputs that can easily be cross-posted by EOSC EDEN and other stakeholders.
- Insights on the role/work of the partner within the EOSC EDEN project.
- Opportunities for collaboration, feedback and participation in events.
- Engagement with ongoing discussions in the field.
- Thought leadership, highlighting key challenges and debates within the scope of the project.
- Include relevant hashtags such as #EOSC, #OpenScience, #HorizonEU, #EuropeanOpenScienceCloud, #EOSChub, #EOSCEDEN, #DigitalPreservation, #EOSCProjects, #OpenAccess. For content that may benefit policy, consider using hashtags like #EUScience, #DataGovernance, #DataPolicy, #DataGovernance
- Cross-post wherever possible.
- Interact with other relevant INFRAEOSC projects, especially the FIDELIS project.
- Tag and acknowledge partners and funding bodies appropriately, wherever possible.

Depending on their local situation or interest, partners are also encouraged to translate the posts into local languages and adapt the messaging depending on the needs of those local stakeholders.

3.4 Coordination mechanisms for joined communication

To ensure coherent and impactful communication, EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS have established a collaborative editorial strategy that aligns their dissemination efforts while respecting the unique identity and contributions

of each project. This strategy is designed to maximize outreach, avoid duplication, and present stakeholders with a unified narrative around digital preservation and EOSC-related developments. At the heart of this coordination is a bi-weekly editorial meeting involving the EOSC EDEN communications team and designated representatives from FIDELIS. These regular touchpoints serve as a dynamic planning and review forum where the teams:

- Share updates on project milestones, stakeholder engagement activities, and upcoming events.
- Coordinate content for the joint website and newsletter, ensuring timely and relevant information is published without overwhelming the audience.
- Align messaging to reflect the synergies between the two projects while clearly distinguishing which activities are led by EOSC EDEN, FIDELIS, or jointly.
- Plan outreach campaigns and social media activities to amplify visibility across the EOSC ecosystem and related communities.
- Monitor engagement metrics (see Table 4) and feedback to refine communication tactics and avoid “audience fatigue” from overlapping or redundant messaging.

This structured yet flexible coordination mechanism ensures that communication remains strategic, consistent, and audience focused. It also supports the effective use of shared tools—such as the joint website and newsletter—by maintaining a clear editorial calendar and content ownership model. Ultimately, this joint approach enhances the visibility and impact of both projects, fosters stronger stakeholder relationships, and contributes to a more integrated and sustainable EOSC communication landscape.

Post Topic	Post type	Project	Lead	Status	Publish Date	Link to post example	LinkedIn Post	Bluesky Post	Newsletter	EOSC Forum
Something about EDEN T1.1 survey results?		EDEN			13/07/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
EOSC Project coordination meeting 2025	SoMe post	EDEN	CSC		26/06/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Reminder about EDEN T1.1 survey closing 30 June	SoMe post	EDEN		Not Started	15/06/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
IPRES 2025 notification of acceptance	SoMe post + websi	EDEN	KU Jevu...	Not Started	03/06/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
EDEN curation school save-the-date	SoMe post + websi	EDEN		Not Started	19/05/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
EDEN T1.1 survey announcement	SoMe post + websi	EDEN		Not Started	05/05/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
Website is Live Announcement	SoMe post	EDEN		Published	02/04/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/post	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
EDEN KoM Day 3	SoMe post	EDEN		Published	06/02/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
EDEN KoM Day 2	SoMe post	EDEN		Published	05/02/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
EDEN KoM Day 1	SoMe post	EDEN		Published	04/02/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
Introduction Post	SoMe post	EDEN		Published	20/01/2025	https://www.linkedin.com/fer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		
EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS in EOSC Landscape		Joint			28/03/2025		<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

Figure 8 – EDEN editorial plan management file

3.5 Accessibility

Social media and other online content should be as inclusive and accessible as possible, ensuring individuals with disabilities can engage with the project's outputs. This includes:

- Alt Text for Images: Where possible, images posted should include descriptive alt text that conveys its meaning for users relying on screen readers.
- Readable Hashtags: Multi-word hashtags should use CamelCase (e.g., #KnowledgeGraphsForHumanities rather than #knowledgegraphsforhumanities) to improve readability for screen readers.
- Captioning and Transcripts: Any video content should include captions, and transcripts should be provided for spoken content where possible.
- Plain Language Summaries: Posts should avoid overly technical language and, where possible, include a simplified summary for broader accessibility.

- Contrast and Font Size Considerations: Images containing text should have sufficient contrast and legible fonts to accommodate users with visual impairments.
- Keyboard Navigation: Any linked content should be designed to be navigable using keyboard—only controls, ensuring accessibility for users who cannot use a mouse.
- Avoiding Excessive Emoji Use: Emojis should be used sparingly and meaningfully, as screen readers will read out each one individually.

Table 3 – KPIs for communication activities in EOSC EDEN

Action	Channels/Tools	Indicator	KPI
Website creation and curation	Website	# of visits (from M3)	B: 100 / S: 1000
Social media posts on project	LinkedIn / Bluesky	# of followers across platform	B: 100 / S: 3000
		# of viewers	B: 100 / S: 3000
Newsletter reach	Newsletter	#of subscribers	B: 50 / S: 450
Video recordings from workshops, webinars, and other events	YouTube / Website	# of viewers	B: 100 / S: 1000

Note: B, beginning of the project; S, summary or the end of the project.

4 Dissemination Plan

To strengthen the use of the key results of EOSC EDEN and knowledge transfer of long-term preservation, and to maximize the impact of the results in the public domain, the target audiences include all potential users of project results, including the scientific community, repositories, archives, European and national Open Science initiatives, policymakers, national funding agencies and individuals in science. The project results will be disseminated through different resources.

4.1 Publication and reporting

As part of the EOSC EDEN DMP and according to the project’s contractual obligations on Open Access, Open Science and Research Data Management, all public documents and reports will be available on the EOSC EDEN Zenodo²⁹ community to ensure public access and so that EOSC EDEN can monitor metrics such as views, citations, and downloads. It is also encouraged to share relevant datasets, provided that all data sharing remains fully compliant with applicable data protection regulations and the project’s data governance policies. Additionally, GitHub will be utilised for software and code development and sharing.

For any plans to submit scientific publications, it is advisable to utilise Diamond Open Access (DOA) publishing venues, e.g., Open Research Europe or other venues complying with EC requirements and recommendations. The publication will be indexed in Zenodo and, gradually, in other major bibliographic databases that accept

²⁹ EOSC EDEN Zenodo Community.

<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosceden/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

ORE for indexing. Other open peer-reviewed scientific journals and collections are also available, such as CODATA Data Science Journal³⁰ and International Journal of Digital Curation.³¹

The release of key outcomes of EOSC EDEN through the Horizon Results Platform⁷ and the EOSC EU Node⁸ will also be exploited.

4.2 Integration into EOSC ecosystem

EOSC EDEN will establish good cooperation and coordination with various INFRAEOSC projects and initiatives in the EOSC ecosystem to reduce redundancies and create synergies. Hence, dissemination of the project's outputs will be targeting also relevant actors under EOSC. EOSC EDEN will run communication campaigns and consultations on awareness, understanding, and maturity of preservation activities in the EOSC ecosystem and beyond, which are open for all to respond to, yet dedicated networks and organisations will be contacted to get sufficient representation and relevant responses. Relevant outputs, when appropriate, will be made available for public consultation through the project website. EOSC EDEN will facilitate calls for feedback (surveys), events, stories, and outcomes, which will also be conducted through the EOSC Forum (reaching the broad EOSC-A membership) and via news items on the communication channels of aligned projects (e.g., newsletter) and initiatives.

To disseminate the outcomes of the EOSC EDEN project, consortium partners should also engage in various events organised by EOSC projects, such as:

- Upcoming versions of the EOSC Symposium: Participate in the large-scale gatherings to present and discuss the latest findings and advancements from EOSC EDEN.
- EOSC Meetings: Attend regular meetings to stay updated on the progress of EOSC initiatives and contribute to ongoing discussions.
- Upcoming versions of the EOSC Winter School: Actively participate to the extent that it is possible, in the relevant Opportunity Areas and sessions.
- Other Events: Engage in various workshops, conferences, and seminars organized by EOSC projects to network with peers and share project outcomes.
- EOSC EDEN has established connections with the EOSC Gravity project and participates in the EOSC Forum and relevant EOSC HE Projects working groups (HE Communication and Engagement WG, HE Technology WG, HE Impact WG). EOSC EDEN had its introductory meeting in March 2025.
- Opportunity Areas:³² A number of EOSC EDEN partner members already participate in relevant Opportunity Areas (OA1 Persistent Identifiers, OA2 Metadata, Ontologies, and Interoperability, OA3 FAIR Assessment and Alignment, OA5 Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling).
- EOSC-A Task Forces: EOSC EDEN has significant presence in the Long-Term Data Retention TF³³ through its partners.
- EOSC HE project's coordination meetings: EOSC EDEN will be represented in the regular meetings organised for pertinent projects by the European Commission and the EOSC-A.
- EOSC macro-roadmap: EOSC EDEN will be contributing with updates on its results to be included in the EOSC macro-roadmap.³⁴

³⁰ CODATA Data Science Journal. <https://datascience.codata.org/>

³¹ International Journal of Digital Curation. <https://www.ijdc.net/index.php/ijdc>

³² <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

³³ <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

³⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-macro-roadmap>

4.3 European Commission Dissemination Tools

To maximise the impact and visibility of the EOSC EDEN results, we will leverage several free-of-charge dissemination and exploitation services³⁵ recommended by the European Commission. REA's communication team can promote project outputs by highlighting and amplifying the news and results through their own and the Commission's social media channels (please tag REA). The project's success story can be proposed for inclusion in the European Commission's free-of-charge communication channels. The below services will be considered during the project to help us reach a broader audience, foster collaborations, and ensure our innovations make it to the market.

- Open Research Europe Platform³⁶: An open-access publishing platform for Horizon Europe beneficiaries, offering open peer review and article revision.
- Horizon Results Platform³⁷: A space to display research results, find collaboration opportunities, and get inspired by others' achievements. It includes Horizon Results Platform TV, which features testimonials and interviews from successful project participants.
- Booster: Provides free consulting services, where applicable, including portfolio dissemination and exploitation strategy, business plan development, and go-to-market support.
- Horizon Standardisation Booster: This offers dedicated support to increase and valorise project results through standardisation for Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects.
- Innovation Radar: Strengthens connections between EU-funded innovators, European investors, and policymakers to help high-potential innovations reach the market.

4.4 Key networks or conferences for dissemination

4.4.1 National Open Science networks

Consortium partners are encouraged to connect with their national or local Open Science networks. This can be achieved by participating in national Open Science (OS) network days, for knowledge exchange about long-term preservation practices, standards, tools, and project outcomes. These events often provide a valuable opportunity for EDEN professionals to share insights and outcomes of the project to Open Science initiative. Consortium partners are also encouraged to present the project results through dedicated virtual webinars aimed at reaching national representatives.

4.4.2 Preservation events, conferences, and project webinars

EOSC EDEN will actively participate in and present the project and findings at prominent preservation conferences (e.g., iPress, PV @CERN, DLF, and NDSA Digital Preservation). These events provide an excellent platform to showcase the project, network with experts, and stay updated on the latest trends and technologies in digital preservation. EOSC EDEN will also host several webinars to engage a broader audience and share results, fostering discussions on best practices and innovative solutions in digital preservation.

4.4.3 Specialist events and conferences / bootcamps

EOSC EDEN will, where applicable, organize co-locate meetings and discussion groups at conferences and events organized by specialist communities (e.g., specific research infrastructure-related events, repository

³⁵ Dissemination and exploitation. https://rea.ec.europa.eu/dissemination-and-exploitation_en#free-of-charge-dissemination-and-exploitation-services

³⁶ Open Research Europe. <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

³⁷ Horizon Results Platform. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/horizon-results-platform>

software community events, etc.). These gatherings provide valuable opportunities to engage with experts, share insights, and foster collaborations within niche areas of digital preservation. Where possible, EOSC EDEN will opt for virtual attendance and presentations to ensure a wider outreach, and leverage hybrid formats to maximize participation and engagement. For instance, participating in hybrid events like ELIXIR’s Data & Interoperability Platform meeting allows for greater flexibility and inclusivity, enabling participants from diverse geographical locations to join and contribute.

Table 4 – KPIs for dissemination activities in EOSC EDEN

Action	Channels/Tools	Indicator	KPI
Publications on project deliverables and other outcomes.	Zenodo Community	# of downloads of the publications	B:10 / S: 300
Scientific publications	Open Access and peer-review journals	# of articles	S: 3
Policy briefing	Zenodo and website	# of briefing	S: 2
EOSC relevant events, e.g., symposiums, winter school	In-person or online meetings	# of events	B:1 / S: 5

Note: B, beginning of the project; S, summary or the end of the project.

5 Collaboration with the FIDELIS Project

Close collaboration with the FIDELIS project, which is establishing a European Network of TDRs, is of utmost importance. EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS are sister projects by design, in the sense that their close collaboration has been a requirement from the funding calls the two projects were addressing. Apart from this contractual obligation, the two projects have early identified the benefits that a close collaboration can provide in terms of leveraging synergies, testing outputs and engaging key stakeholders, thus maximising impact. FIDELIS’ input will be crucial when it comes to requirements for the TDRs, frameworks, standards, and tools developed by EOSC EDEN. The collaboration with FIDELIS will also be relevant for the sustainable embedding of the EOSC EDEN outcomes into existing organisational contexts to ensure the continued maintenance and extension of the assets produced by the project. EOSC EDEN will seek to provide its outputs for testing, feedback and adoption, using as platform, among others, the FIDELIS support programme in any way deemed appropriate (e.g. through the FIDELIS cascading grants mechanism, mentorship programme or open training interventions). In addition, FIDELIS’ call for work on a network of trusted repositories is critical to EOSC EDEN, as the project can complement the network with long-term digital transformation players.

At this point in time, EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS are both in the process of analysing the results of individual surveys targeting the stakeholder category with regards to special characteristics and needs for engagement and training. A survey targeting the two consortia has been implemented in the context of EOSC EDEN, aiming to provide information for a Matrix of known and emerging networks of service providers, including repositories and registries (Milestone M4.1). This milestone, in the form of an internal report, aims to consolidate the results on information across EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS with regards to known and emerging networks of service providers (including repositories and registries) that are of relevance for the two projects, and highlight the characteristics, challenges for the planning of relevant EOSC EDEN (and shared with FIDELIS) engagement activities. The Matrix can be found in Appendix 3 of this document.

5.1 Collaboration points

The main objectives of collaboration points with FIDELIS regarding engagement and communication include:

- **Ensure alignment and synchronisation of the two projects:** The two projects complement each other, as EOSC EDEN is a Research and Innovation Action (RIA), focusing on developing new solutions, while FIDELIS is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), aiming to facilitate collaboration, alignment, and uptake across initiatives. The two projects aim to be consistent, synchronised and align in the topics and activities that are common.
- **Streamline engagement of common stakeholders:** Collaborate with the sister project FIDELIS to ensure that existing and aspiring TDRs, trusted repositories, established as a European network of TDRs through FIDELIS, will provide feedback for and will be approached for testing, adoption and long-term sustainability of the tools and services are easily findable, identifiable, and described in the EOSC EDEN registry. For this reason, a joint website and newsletter have been developed to ensure coordinated communication.
- **Collaboration in events:** The two projects will collaborate, when appropriate, in co-organising and participating in meetings and events, to maximise impact while using the available resources reasonably. One significant example of this practice is the co-organisation of a shared kick-off meeting. Furthermore, a dedicated session was organised during the EOSC EDEN – FIDELIS Joint Kick-off meeting (4-6 February 2025) in Helsinki, Finland, to understand and align the work plans of the two projects. The main objectives of the kick-off meeting were: (1) getting to know each other, (2) reaching an agreement on the first 12 months' work, (3) identifying and discussing potential challenges, and (4) identifying collaboration areas between EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS, understand dependencies, agree on coordination mechanisms, and align timelines.

5.2 Strategic Alliance, joint Project Management Board and Coordination mechanism

In EOSC EDEN the effort on establishing Strategic Alliance is led by the work on *Coordination, Sustainability and Strategic Alignment* (WP5), which ensures strategic alignment with the EOSC Partnership and other relevant strategic initiatives in Europe, including FIDELIS, also with the support of the External Advisory Board. Under this work potential exploitation and sustainability pathways after the end of the project for the outputs and the network(s) created in the context of EOSC EDEN will be explored in collaboration with FIDELIS, where appropriate. Regular joint project management board (PMB) meetings are organised between EOSC EDEN and FIDELIS to discuss and ensure strategic alignment. These 1-hour bi-monthly meetings will be organised online and based on the agenda; different partners from the project will be invited to contribute.

The External Advisory Board (EAB) consists of independent experts outside of the consortium who have volunteered to support the project in achieving its objectives and to help maximise the project's impact. The EAB will not only provide recommendations for the PMB regarding the project and its outcomes, but they will also act as ambassadors of the project and its results in relevant communities and initiatives. EDEN's PMB and EAB will meet twice per year either online or in person.

A coordination mechanism is being set up between the two projects to ensure regular interaction and alignment with regards to solutions proposed for repositories. This coordination mechanism will act as the mediator body between the two projects that will ensure that a) the solutions developed in EOSC EDEN, and

especially the Service Registry and Selection Guidance, take into account the requirement of trustworthiness provided by FIDELIS, and that b) the outputs of EOSC EDEN are provided as solutions for adoption to the repositories supported by FIDELIS in their journey towards reaching maturity in being trustworthy. Regular meetings will be facilitated where EOSC EDEN will have the opportunity to pitch their solutions to EOSC projects and networks as well as three Bootcamps for repositories, archives and registries will be organised (see section on engagement mechanisms). This coordination mechanism will be established and supported by the EOSC EDEN work on *Engagement and synchronisation with relevant EOSC projects and networks* (T4.3) and will operate under the auspices of the shared Project Management Board.

A minimum of three joint meetings will be organised, two face-to-face and one remotely, for cross-fertilisation activities of the two projects. The events will be collocated with one of the major events of one of the two projects to reduce costs and travel. The 1-day meetings will be crucial to check the progress on the items in scope for the collaboration.

6 Monitoring and evaluation

To assess the effectiveness of engagement efforts, EOSC EDEN has defined metrics such as the number of stakeholders reached, the level of participation, and the quality of feedback. EOSC EDEN will regularly evaluate activities (annually) against objectives and adjust strategies as needed. Communication, dissemination, and engagement results will be updated during the regular project meetings and the EOSC EDEN WIKI to inform project improvements and highlight success stories. The final Communications, Dissemination, and Engagement Report will be created based on this responsive plan in month 36 as a deliverable of D4.3.

6.1 High-level Key Performance Indicators

In addition to the aforementioned KPIs for engagement, communication, and dissemination activities, EOSC EDEN will adopt four high-level KPIs to effectively assess the project's overall scale and impact. See the table below for details.

Table 5 – High-level key performance indicators of EOSC EDEN

Measure	Baseline (M0)	Value (M36)
KPI 1: The frameworks, services, and protocols are codesigned and tested with different types of stakeholders (including researchers, trustworthy repositories and archives, commercial providers, and other types of providers).	0	>10 different disciplines
KPI 2: The outcomes of the project are disseminated in national, European, and global venues.	0	Results disseminated >2 global (e.g., RDA and CODATA events), 2 EU (e.g., EOSC Symposia), and 10 national events
KPI 3: The proof of concept of the integration of the registry in the EOSC Federation is completed, and the services are available for the EOSC Federation via an existing Node.	TRL: 3	TRL: 9
KPI 4: Curation skills in Europe are strengthened: 1) Two curation workshops are organised with at least 50 participants; 2) A	0	50 curation experts trained, and a curation network counting at least

curation network will be operational after the end of the project to maintain and evolve the assets developed by the project.		100 individuals geographically distributed in the EU
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6.2 Requirements and potential barriers

The following requirements and potential obstacles could influence the success of engagement with the relevant stakeholders or dissemination of the project outcome, especially the collaboration with FIDELIS, engagement in data quality and curation, and the most relevant stakeholders.

Table 6 –Challenges for the effective implementation of engagement and dissemination activities

Requirements	Potential Barriers	Mitigation Measures
Collaboration with FIDELIS	Non-efficient or difficult collaboration	Synchronise with the FIDELIS project to align both work plans.
		Joint Project Management Board meetings. A joint kick-off meeting was held in Feb 2025.
		Resources have been earmarked in the project to facilitate such collaboration
Engagement in data quality and curation experts	Lack of engagement	Organise two curation workshops to train potential curators.
		Travel grants have been reserved.
		Provide knowledge value and will “go to the community”
Adoption by the most relevant stakeholders	Lack of adoption	Use cases and pilots engaging potential users of the services have been included in the work plan.
		Requirements collection activities and consultation with the stakeholders have been included in the work plan.
		Joint communication and dissemination activities with FIDELIS.
		Representatives of potential user communities and organisations have been invited as part of the EAB

7 Conclusions

This document presents the communication, dissemination, and engagement plan of EOSC EDEN, which was developed within the framework of WP4 - Expert & Community Engagement. The plan aims to guide and coordinate a set of targeted actions targeted at raising awareness, promoting engagement, and maximising uptake of the outcomes of the EOSC EDEN. This document was jointly developed and agreed upon by the EOSC EDEN partners and reflects a shared commitment to the successful implementation of the plan. It outlines a roadmap of activities tailored to different stakeholders to ensure the success of the EOSC EDEN. Each partner is expected to actively contribute to the delivery of these activities according to the level of effort and responsibilities defined in the EOSC EDEN work plan. The plan serves as a living guide to adapt and respond to emerging needs and opportunities throughout the project lifecycle. The initial version of this document was released on the 30th of June 2025. An updated version will be released at month 18 and a final communication, dissemination and engagement report will be published in month 36, which will include activities and events executed throughout the project.

8 Annexes

Appendix 1. Stakeholder engagement plan in each work package of EOSC EDEN.

Appendix 2. Key facts of EOSC EDEN.

Appendix 3. Survey results M4.1 Matrix of known and emerging networks of service providers, including repositories and registries.

Appendix 1. Stakeholder engagement plan in each work package of EOSC EDEN.

WP	Primary Stakeholders	Engagement Activity
WP1 - Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generic and discipline-specific communities, • CoreTrustSeal, nestor Seal, ISO 16363, RDA TRUST, EOSC TF • Repositories, archives, FIDELIS, policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Desk research and surveys; Creation of checklists • Guidelines, and sample policies • Taking existing guidelines and frameworks • Liaison to identify additional qualitative metrics • Developing sample policies
WP2 - Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PAR, GORC, OAIS sources, FIDELIS • INFRAEOSC projects, e.g., OSTrails, FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIR-IMPACT & ARCHIVER. • EOSC Federation & Node 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landscape analysis and user requirements • Reuses and extends multiple EU-funded project outputs • Define joint development and test process
WP3 - Discipline-Specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discipline-specific communities, RDA, GO FAIR • Disciplinary partners in WP3 • EOSC-A TFs and projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create survey question content; Semi-structured interviews; discipline-oriented analysis and integration • Workshops, user journey map, testing, validation, and advice • Using methods developed in previous EOSC projects, building on existing recommendations
WP4 - Expert & Community Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium partners • Service provider networks, EOSC Federation. • INFRAEOSC projects, especially, FIDELIS) • Cultural heritage organisations, GLAM, Common European Data Spaces, policymakers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form a discussion platform; Develop a portfolio of virtual and physical activities; provide support • Establish an expert curation network, two curation workshops • Engagement and synchronisation; Identification of alignment and coordination opportunities re: engagement of service provider networks; Bootcamps; (virtual) engagement at national level • Run consultations; Provide the project website, newsletter, socials, and produce content; Support; Coordinate and connect the outreach
WP5 - Coordination, Sustainability and Strategic Alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consortium partners, Funding agency, EC, EAB • EAB, EOSC-A and TFs and Partnership, Data Spaces, FIDELIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project coordination and liaison, reporting coordination and preparation; DMP; Internal communication mechanisms; Organise project meetings • Liaisons, Organise project meetings

Appendix 2. Key facts of EOSC EDEN.

Key Facts	Details
Project acronym	EOSC EDEN
Project full title	Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at the European and National level
Project start and end date	1 Jan 2025 - 31 Dec 2027
Project duration	36 months
Funding	Horizon Europe, Grant agreement ID: 101188015
Programme(s)	HORIZON.1.3 - Research infrastructures (Main Program) HORIZON.1.3.1 - Consolidating and Developing the Landscape of European Research Infrastructures
Topic(s)	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-04 - Long-term access and preservation infrastructure development for EOSC, including data quality aspects
DOI	10.3030/101188015
Project partners	<p>16 in total</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus ● Technische Informationsbibliothek (TIB) ● Koninklijke Nederlandse Akademie van Wetenschappen - KNAW ● Universitetet i Tromsø - Norges Arktiske Universitet ● Katholieke Universiteit Leuven ● University of Essex ● Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire ● Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH ● SURF BV ● Universität Bremen ● Comité des Données Scientifiques et Technologiques Association ● Stichting Open Preservation (NL) ● Arkivum Limited ● Premotec Poland Sp. z o.o. ● Premotec GmbH ● SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics
Work packages	<p>5 WPs in total</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● WP1 Data and Process Framework for Long-Term Digital Preservation ● WP2 Long-term Access and Preservation Services & Tools ● WP3 Discipline-specific Requirements, Validation and Future Use ● WP4 Expert & Community Engagement ● WP5 Coordination, Sustainability, and Strategic Alignment

D.4.1 Responsive communication, dissemination, and engagement plan

Appendix 3. Survey results M4.1 Matrix of known and emerging networks of service providers, including repositories and registries.

A/A	Network	Stakeholder group(s)	Reach	Discipline	Sector	Opportunities for engagement	Connectors
1	AVOTT https://avointiede.fi/en/open-science-coordination	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	National (FI)	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	Open science event twice a year and smaller events avointiede.fi/en/eventpage	TAU-FSD
2	EOSC Poland Network https://eosc.gov.pl/en/eosc-poland-network/	Service providers	National (PL)	Multidisciplinary	Public sector	N/A	Gdańsk Tech; KMD4EOSC
3	Fairdata NETWORK https://www.fairdata.fi/en/fairdata-network/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	National (FI)	Multidisciplinary	Both	Several network meetings during the year www.fairdata.fi/en/fairdata-network/	TAU-FSD
4	FID Netzwerk https://wikis.su.b.uni-hamburg.de/webis/index.php/FID-Netzwerk	Repositories; Archives; Registries	National (DE)	Multidisciplinary	Public sector	Annual Member Meeting; various webinars and special interest group meetings throughout the year	TIB
5	GLAM collaboration https://www.digime.fi/en/	Repositories; Archives	National (FI)	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	(Bi)annual seminars, monthly open hours digitalpreservation.fi/resources/events www.digime.fi/en/	TAU-FSD
6	KoopLZV (no public website)	Service providers; Archives	National (DE)	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	N/A	TIB
7	National Research Data Curation Network of Norway https://septentrio.uit.no/index.php/SCS/article/view/7733	Repositories	National (NO)	Domain-agnostic	Both	Not decided yet.	UiT
8	nestor https://www.dn.b.de/EN/Professionell/Projekte/Kooperationen/nestor/nestor_node.html	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	National (DE)	Domain-agnostic	Both	Wiki for internal communication; meetings 3-4 times per year	TIB

D.4.1 Responsive communication, dissemination, and engagement plan

9	NFDI https://www.nfdi.de/?lang=en	Repositories; Archives; Registries	National (DE)	Multidisciplinary	Public sector	Frequent meetings across NFDI consortia, including monthly BiodiversityTea, biweekly NFDI4Earth Coffee Lectures, and annual project conferences. More: http://www.nfdi.de/termine/	TIB; UBREMEN
10	Recherche Data Gouv https://entrepot.recherche.data.gouv.fr/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	National (FR)	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	https://www.metrofood.eu/	INRAE; MESR; Skills4EOSC
11	SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics https://www.sib.swiss/	Service providers; Repositories	National (CH)	Domain-specific (life sciences, bioinformatics)	Public sector	Has several working groups	SIB; EOSC; FIDELIS; EOSC Data Commons
12	BlueCloud2026 https://bluecloud.org/	Service providers; Archives; Registries	European project	Domain-specific (physical sciences, earth science)	Both	https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/	CSIC
13	Cern Document Server https://cds.cern.ch/	Service providers; Repositories	European	Multidisciplinary	Public sector	One every three months.	CERN
14	CESSDA ERIC https://www.CESSDA.eu/About	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	European	Domain-specific (social sciences)	Public sector	https://www.dpconline.org/events or Annual conference. https://the-hsraa.org/ or https://www.biocuration.org/events/	CESSDA ERIC, TAU-FSD, Sikt, UESSEX-UKDA; KNAW-DANS; FIDELIS; OSTrails; ONTOLISST; OSCARS
15	CLARIN https://www.clarin.eu/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	European	Domain-specific (social science / humanities, linguistics)	Both	SIB organises one event per year for its community (SIB Days, even-numbered years, BC2 odd-numbered years). CLARIN Conference will take place in October 2025.	UiT; CLARIN
16	ELIXIR https://elixir-europe.org/	Service providers; Repositories	European	Domain-specific (life science)	Public sector	ELIXIR organises every year: - An all Hands meeting, to review ELIXIR's recent achievements and activities, and to discuss	SIB

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						future plans. - The Biohackathon Europe, an intense week of hacking, with over 160 international participants, to work on diverse and exciting projects.	
17	EMODNET https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en	Service providers; Archives; Registries	European	Domain-specific (physical sciences, earth science)	Both	https://emodnet.ec.europa.eu/en/events	CSIC
18	EOSC https://eosc.eu/	Service providers; Repositories	European	Multidisciplinary	Both	https://eosc.eu/	Most partners are involved in the EOSC
19	EUDAT https://eudat.eu/	Service providers	European	Multidisciplinary	Both	biennial	DKRZ
20	METROFOOD https://www.metrofood.eu/	Service providers; Repositories	European	Domain-specific (life sciences, food science)	Both	CLARIN Annual Conference/Annual/ https://www.clarin.eu/content/clarin-annual-conference	PMT PL; EOSC Beyond
21	SeaDataNet https://www.seadatanet.org/	Service providers; Archives; Registries	European	Domain-specific (physical sciences, earth science)	Both	https://www.seadatanet.org/Events	CSIC
22	AUDS https://www.sg.ch/kultur/staatsarchiv/Spezialthemen/auds.html	Archives	National ; European	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	German speaking network (members from Germany, Austria, Switzerland, Luxembourg, Czech Republic) with Annual conference	TIB
23	BioAlps https://bioalps.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Registries	National ; Global	Domain-specific	Both	LS2 and ISB: Annual meetings BioAlps: meetings throughout the year, in Switzerland and internationally, organised by the network or supported by it.	SIB
24	CoreTrustSeal https://www.coretrustseal.org/	Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	biodiversitea: https://nfdi4biodiversity.org/de/events/biodiversitea-11/ annual project meetings	KNAW-DANS; Gdańsk Tech; TAU-FSD; DKRZ; TIB; KU Leuven
25	DataCite https://datacite.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	e.g. DataCite Open Hours, https://datacite.org/events/ , DataCite Annual Community Meetings/Annual/ https://datacite.org/datacite-community-meetings/	UBREMEN; KU Leuven; UiT

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26	DDI Alliance https://ddialliance.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Several events, e.g. annual meetings, developers meetings https://ddialliance.org/ In addition, DDI Alliance endorses e.g. the annual European DDI Users Conference (EDDI) https://www.eddi-conferences.eu/	TAU-FSD
27	Digital Curation Centre https://dcc.ac.uk/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Annual International Digital Curation Conference	UEDIN/DCC; KNAW-DANS; TIB
28	DPC https://www.dpconline.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Frequent online events and webinars, including biannual community seminars, an Annual Member Meeting, and strong presence at iPRES. More info: https://www.dpconline.org/events	Arkivum, KU Leuven, TIB
29	ESGF https://esgf-metagrid.cloud.dkrz.de/search/esgf-dkrz/	Repositories	Global	Domain-specific (physical sciences, earth science)	Public sector	N/A	DKRZ
30	EuroFIR https://www.eurofir.org/	Repositories	European; Global	Domain-specific (life sciences, food science)	Both	https://www.eurofir.org/	PMT PL
31	Global Dataverse Community Consortium https://www.gdccc.io/	Repositories	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Dataverse Community Meeting/Annual/ https://dataverse.org/events and https://www.gdccc.io/working-groups.html	KU Leuven; UiT
32	Goblet https://www.mygoblet.org/about/	Service providers; Registries	Global	Domain-specific (life sciences, bioinformatics)	Public sector	Goblet events include Train-the-Trainer events, Conferences, Annual General Meetings and more. https://www.mygoblet.org/events/	SIB
33	HSRAA https://the-hsraa.org/	Service providers; Archives	Global	Domain-specific (life sciences, healthcare)	Private sector	N/A	Arkivum
34	IASSIST https://iassistdata.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Multidisciplinary	Both	Service Providers' Forum twice a year. Various other events www.cessda.eu	TAU-FSD; FIDELIS; OSTrails; ONTOLISST; OSCARS
35	ICPSR https://www.icp	Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-specific	Both	Several events, e.g. biennial meetings,	TAU-FSD

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	sr.umich.edu/web/pages/			(social sciences, social research)		https://www.icpsr.umich.edu https://www.icpsr.umich.edu/web/membership/cms/4611	
36	InvenioRDM https://inveniordm.web.cern.ch/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	National ; European; Global	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	Comms/Tech Clinics Monthly. As above.	CERN
37	iPRES https://ipres-conference.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	https://ipres-conference.org/ Annual iPRES International Conference on Digital Preservation	KU Leuven, TIB
38	ISB https://www.biorxiv.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-specific (life sciences, biocuration)	Both	LS2 and ISB: Annual meetings BioAlps: meetings throughout the year, in Switzerland and internationally, organised by the network or supported by it.	SIB; EOSC Data Commons
39	ISDFPN https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/about/research-and-development/international-secure-data-facility-professionals-network-isdfpn/	Repositories	Global	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	Quarterly https://ukdataservice.ac.uk/about/research-and-development/international-secure-data-facility-professionals-network-isdfpn/	UESSEX-UKDA / UKDS-UESSEX
40	LS2 https://www.ls2.ch/	Service providers; Repositories; Registries	National ; Global	Domain-specific (life sciences)	Both	LS2 and ISB: Annual meetings BioAlps: meetings throughout the year, in Switzerland and internationally, organised by the network or supported by it.	SIB
41	NatLA https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/discover-good-practice/working-groups-and-task-forces	Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	Every other month virtually, once per year f2f (in conjunction with the iPRES conference series)	TIB
42	OpenAIRE http://www.openaire.eu/	Service providers; Repositories	European; Global	Multidisciplinary	Both	Regular Coffee lectures and working group meetings	UoB; KNAW-DANS; OpenAIRE Advance; NI4OS Europe
43	OPF https://openpreservation.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	nestor Praxistag (yearly); various webinars, podcasts, working group meetings, etc. https://www.langzeitarchivierung.de/ , biennial https://worlddatasystem.org/news-events/idw2025/	TIB, OPFNL

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44	PREMIS Editorial Board https://www.loc.gov/standards/premis/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Interial Editorial Committee meetings monthly; meetings for the wider PREMIS community in form of webinars / tutorials / implementation fairs approx twice a year (often connected to conferences)	TIB
45	Rosetta User Group https://igelu.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives	Global	Domain-agnostic	Both	Annual f2f meeting of International Rosetta Users; monthly Steering Committee calls plus monthly working group calls. https://igelu.org/products-and-initiatives/product-working-groups/rosetta/	KU Leuven, TIB
46	Safe Data Access Professionals https://securedatagroup.org/	Repositories	Global	Domain-agnostic	Public sector	Quarterly https://securedatagroup.org/events/	UESSEX-UKDA / UKDS-UESSEX
47	World Data System https://worlddata.system.org/	Repositories; Archives	Global	Multidisciplinary	Public sector	Different working groups have events. Rate of occurrence varies. Annual conference, various online events throughout the year iassistdata.org/conferences iassistdata.org/community	EOSC Data Commons; KNAW-DANS, UBREMEN, DKRZ
48	Zenodo https://zenodo.org/	Service providers; Repositories; Archives; Registries	Global	Multidisciplinary	Both	N/A	OPFNL; CERN